

SHORT NOTES

Effect of Alkali on the Reduction of Potassium Permanganate by Selenium Dioxide

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In the earlier publications (Lal *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 167; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 162) it has been reported that reduction of permanganates by selenium dioxide, in the acidic medium, yields selenic acid, the metal selenate, manganous selenite, manganic diselenite, manganese selenate (only traces), and a complex compound, $xR_2O \cdot yMnO \cdot zMnO_2$. The present work has been undertaken with a view to studying the effect of alkali on various reaction products.

Procedure.—To a 1% $KMnO_4$ solution (50 c.c.), made alkaline with 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 c.c. of *N*-KOH solution respectively, a 5% aqueous solution of selenium dioxide was dropped slowly to just discharge the pink colour. The filtrates and precipitates were analysed completely.

The medium of reaction, which became finally alkaline, passed through acidic and neutral stages. The analytical results of the end products show that almost similar products are formed in the acidic and the neutral media while in the alkaline medium these differ considerably (Table I). The results obtained in the alkaline medium have further been verified by studying all the three stages of reduction of potassium permanganate by potassium selenite (Table II).

It appears that selenic acid, produced in the reaction, is neutralised by the free alkali with the result that as the volume of *N*-KOH added increases, the amount of acid decreases, and potassium selenate content subsequently increases. Existence of potassium oxide, which is noticed even in the acidic medium, is probably due to the reason that this is firmly held by the hydrated manganese dioxide, possessing feebly acidic properties. Formation of manganese selenate in the acidic and neutral media may be regarded to be produced as a result of direct interaction of the freshly precipitated hydrated manganese dioxide and selenium dioxide. In the coloured stage, manganese selenate is, however, acted upon by the unused permanganate, and therefore it disappears completely. In the alkaline medium, the absence may be due to its reaction with free alkali. Both manganous selenite and manganic diselenite are most probably acted upon by the free alkali and the resulting potassium selenite is further oxidised by the oxygen liberated by the mutual interaction of permanganate and free alkali, as suggested by Sackur and Taegerer (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1912, 18, 718).

TABLE I
Analyses of reaction mixtures obtained when alkaline 1% KMnO_4 (50 c.c.) solution is just decolorised with 5% SeO_3 solution.

No.	N-KOH added	SeO_3 soln. required.	Medium.	K_2SeO_4	Filtrate. KOH.	H_2SeO_4	Precipitate. MnSeO_3	$\text{Mn}_2\text{Se}_2\text{O}_7$	K_2O	MnO.	MnO_2	Approx. mol. ratio. $\text{K}_2\text{O}:\text{MnO}:\text{MnO}_2$
1.	{ 4.00 4.00	13.70 13.70	Acidic	0.7367g.	0.2393g.		0.0399g.	0.0358g.	0.0241g.	0.0429g.	0.1945g.	1:2.9
				0.7352	Nil	0.0396	0.0361	0.0229	0.0427	0.1942	1:2.9	
2.	{ 6.00 6.00	13.80 13.80	"	0.9630	0.1187		0.0331	0.0266	0.0237	0.0474	0.1931	1:3.9
				0.9597	0.1179		0.0333	0.0261	0.0223	0.0469	0.1928	1:3.9
3.	{ 8.00 8.00	13.70 13.70	Neutral	1.1599	0.0		0.0254	0.0164	0.0304	0.0510	0.1935	1:2.7
				1.1632	Nil	0.0248	0.0160	0.0300	0.0520	0.1931	1:2.7	
4. "	{ 10.00 10.00	13.20 13.20	Alkaline	1.1768	0.0740		Nil	Nil	0.0584	0.0732	0.1850	1:2.3
				1.1749	0.0759		Nil	Nil	0.0588	0.0728	0.1844	1:2.3
5.	{ 12.00 12.00	13.10 13.15	"	1.1782	0.1848		Nil	Nil	0.0585	0.0740	0.1846	1:2.3
				1.1756	0.1872		Nil	Nil	0.0582	0.0736	0.1842	1:2.3

TABLE II

No.	K_2SeO_3 soln. added	Stage of reaction.	KMnO_4 decomp.	K_2SeO_4	Filtrate. KOH.	K_2SeO_3 unused.	Precipitate. K_2O	MnO.	MnO_2	Approx. mol. ratio. $\text{K}_2\text{O}:\text{MnO}:\text{MnO}_2$
*1.	{ 9.60 9.60	Coloured	54.92%	0.5237g.	0.0511g.	Nil	0.0330	0.0458	0.0940	1:2.3
			54.92	0.5315	0.0511	0.0332	0.0458	0.0943	1:2.3	
*2.	{ 14.40 14.00	"	80.00	0.7782	0.0911	"	0.0426	0.0667	0.1368	1:2.3
			80.00	0.7775	0.0911	0.0424	0.0663	0.1362	1:2.3	
3.	{ 19.20 19.20	Intermediate	100.00	1.0410	0.1122	"	0.0543	0.0834	0.1708	1:2.3
			100.00	1.0398	0.1122	0.0544	0.0839	0.1711	1:2.3	
4.	{ 21.70 21.70	Colorless	100.00	1.0434	0.1172	0.1232g.	0.0545	0.0848	0.1701	1:2.3
			100.00	1.0440	0.1155	0.1209	0.0546	0.0852	0.1708	1:2.3
5.	{ 24.20 24.20	"	100.00	1.0420	0.1206	0.2484	0.0544	0.0836	0.1704	1:2.3
			100.00	1.0427	0.1206	0.2462	0.0545	0.0836	0.1711	1:2.3

* The reaction mixtures were filtered after an interval of about 24 hours.